

ROLE OF AYURVEDA IN NUTRITIONAL DISORDERS**Vd. Renuka S. Jambhorkar¹, Vd. Sneha Tiwari^{2*}**¹Professor, Balroga Shri K. R. Pandav Ayurved College, Nagpur.²Associate Professor, Kayachikista Shri K. R. Pandav Ayurved College, Nagpur.***Corresponding Author: Vd. Sneha Tiwari**

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INTRODUCTION

Malnutrition, in every form, presents significant threats to human health. Today, the world faces a double burden of malnutrition that includes both undernutrition and overweight, especially in low- and middle-income countries. There are multiple forms of malnutrition, including undernutrition (wasting or stunting), inadequate vitamins or minerals, overweight, obesity, and resulting diet-related noncommunicable diseases. Ayurvedic nutrition is a holistic approach to diet and wellness rooted in ancient Indian traditions. It is based on the principles of Ayurveda, a system of medicine that has been practiced in India for thousands of years. There are three main Doshas: Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. Each Dosha is associated with specific qualities and elements, and individuals are believed to have different Prakriti based on these Doshas that influence their physical, mental, and emotional characteristics. PEM is a disorder marked by insufficient consumption of protein and/or energy (calories), which can result in a number of nutritional disorders and health problems.

In Ayurvedic nutrition, foods are classified according to Rasas and their effects on the Doshas. A balanced diet includes all six Rasas, with an emphasis on foods that pacify or balance your dominant Dosha. Ayurvedic nutrition also emphasizes the importance of mindful eating, eating seasonal foods, and following a daily routine that aligns with the natural rhythms of the body and the environment. It considers factors such as food combinations, cooking methods, and the time of day when food is consumed. In Ayurveda, nutritional disorders are understood in terms of Doshas (Vata, Pitta, and Kapha) and imbalances in the Agni. When these imbalances occur, they can cause various health problems related to nutrition and digestion. Some of the common nutritional disorders in Ayurveda include Balashosha, Parigarbhika, Phakka roga, obesity, etc. Malnutrition occurs when the digestive system is unable to properly absorb nutrients from food. Ayurveda cites Mandagni or imbalanced Doshas as the cause of decreased absorption. In Balashosha, there is emaciation of the body due to depletion of subcutaneous fat and tissue. Parigarbhika highlights the development of malnutrition during the infancy period. Phakka is a clinical manifestation (symptom) with continuous

deterioration of growth associated with delayed motor developmental milestones. Ayurveda sees obesity as an imbalance of the Kapha dosha, which is associated with heaviness, excess, and stagnation. To remove this imbalance, herbal remedies are often recommended, as well as changes in diet and lifestyle.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To study the Nutritional disorders

To study the role of Ayurveda in the management of nutritional disorders, including all the drugs and formulations.

Protein Energy Malnutrition (PEM): The World Health Organization (WHO) defines malnutrition as “the cellular imbalance between the supply of nutrients and energy and the body's demand for them to ensure growth, maintenance, and specific functions.” The term protein-energy malnutrition (PEM) applies to a group of related disorders that include marasmus, kwashiorkor, and intermediate states of marasmus-kwashiorkor. IAP classification of malnutrition: This classification is based on weight for age values.

Grade of malnutrition	Weight-for-age of standard (%)
Normal	> 80
Grade 1	71-80 (mild malnutrition)
Grade 2	61-70 (moderate malnutrition)
Grade 3	51-60 (severe malnutrition)
Grade 4	< 50 (very severe malnutrition)

Marasmus: Marasmus is starvation in infants occurring due to an overall lack of calories.

Kwashiorkor: Kwashiorkor is related to protein deficiency, though calorie intake may be sufficient.

Feature	Kwashiorkor	Marasmus
Definition	Protein deficiency with sufficient calorie intake	Starvation in infants with an overall lack of calories
Clinical Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Occurs in children between 6 months and 3 years of age Growth failure Wasting of muscles but preserved adipose tissue Oedema, localised or generalised, present Enlarged fatty liver Serum proteins low Anaemia present 'Flag sign'- Alternate bands of light (depigmented) and dark (pigmented) hair 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common in infants under 1 year of age Growth failure Wasting of all tissues including muscles and adipose tissue Oedema present No hepatic enlargement Serum proteins low Anaemia present Monkey- like face, protuberant abdomen, thin limbs
Morphology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enlarged fatty liver Atrophy of different tissues and organs but subcutaneous fat preserved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fatty liver Atrophy of different tissues and organs including subcutaneous fat

Balashosha: This disease is explained by Vagbhatta. The cause of Balashosha is Shlaishmika anna sevana (Excessive energy-dense food), Shitambupana (drinking cold water), and Divaswapna (excessive day sleep), drinking breast milk vitiated by Shleshma- by these, the channel of Rasa (first fluid liquid) gets blocked by Kapha. Clinical features are Arochaka (Reduced digestive capacity), Pratishyaya (running nose), Jwara (fever), Kasa (cough), and Snigdha shukla mukha Akshi. These conditions, if not detected early, may lead to

Shosha (emaciation) with its eyes being unctuous (grassy) and white.

Parigarbhika: A Child fed breast milk from a pregnant mother who has Alpa Poshakansha (poor nutrients) leads to Parigarbhika. If a breastfeeding mother (within one year) becomes pregnant again, it will result in a decreased breast milk secretion as hormones maintaining pregnancy and breast milk secretion are contradictory in action. Hence, there will be a stoppage or a decrease in

adequate breast milk secretion, and the first child will be deprived of breast milk in its Ksheerada Avastha.

Phakka Roga: Phakka-Roga is a unique and the only nutritional disorder or Kuposhanjanya Vyadhi explained by Kashyapa. It is a clinical manifestation (symptom) with continuous deterioration of growth associated with delayed motor development milestones. Due to a running-down condition, the child is immunocompromised.

Ayurveda Drugs for Nutritional Disorders

Ayurvedic medicine identified several herbs or compound compositions that have a therapeutic and preventive impact on nutritional diseases. These medications function because of certain characteristics and ingredients found in various plant parts. The role of some drugs is described as follows.

Shatavari is a powerful rejuvenator; it gives women's hormones and is used to help them feel better. It boosts the functioning of several organs and aids in immunity maintenance.

Yashtimadhu: It provides the minerals needed to keep the gastrointestinal tract healthy, soothes moderate laxative pain, relaxes tense muscles, and boosts immunity with its antioxidant activity.

Pippali: Thus, Pippali's digestive system stimulant fights against nutritional deficiencies brought on by compromised digestion. It aids in restoring hormonal equilibrium and releasing metabolic energy.

Haritaki: Because it is a tonic, Haritaki helps with the physical debility brought on by starvation. Like Pippali, Haritaki transforms Ahara into nutritious Rasa to improve digestion and preserve nutritional supplies. Haritaki is a strong source of vitamin C and supports overall health.

Ashwagandha: Ashwagandha is a revitalizing herb that feeds the body's physical and mental well-being. It has tonic properties and aids in the treatment of general malnutrition-related debility.

CONCLUSION

Nutrition is a critical part of health and development. Better nutrition is related to improved infant, child, and maternal health, stronger immune systems, safer pregnancy and childbirth, lower risk of non-communicable diseases (such as diabetes and cardiovascular disease), and longevity. PEM is a serious worldwide health issue, especially for communities experiencing poverty, food instability, and restricted access to nutrient-dense diets, as well as those living in emerging nations. According to Ayurveda, the nutritional disorders are Balashosha, Parigarbhika, Phakka roga, and Obesity, have been aggravated due to the Mandagni. Ama is the primary cause of Mandagni. Shunthi, Ajwain, and Jeera are the Agnideepaka dravyas that treat Ama. This is how Rasavaha srotodushti is being treated. The root cause of all these nutritional diseases is Rasavaha srotodushti. The most effective Aushadha yogas for

nutritional diseases are those Dravyas that act on Rasavaha srotodushti.

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